

Live cell biosensors based on the fluorescence lifetime of environment-sensing dyes

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NMR and high-resolution mass spectra

¹H NMR spectrum of S2 (CDCl₃, 400 MHz).

^{13}C NMR spectrum of S2 (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz).

High resolution mass spectrum of S2.

S2_Repeat_20230726103108 #1-40 RT: 0.01-0.52 AV: 40 NL: 2.97E9
T: FTMS + p ESI Full ms [150.0000-2000.0000]

obsd 380.0946, calcd 380.0951

^{13}C NMR spectrum of mero81 (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz).

High resolution mass spectrum of mero81.

mero-81_20230620085651 #1-99 RT: 0.01-1.28 AV: 99 NL: 7.60E8
T: FTMS + p ESI Full ms [150.0000-2000.0000]

obsd 418.1478, calcd 418.1471

¹H NMR spectrum of S3 (DMSO-d₆, 850 MHz).

High resolution mass spectrum of S3.

PV-177 Repeat #1-99 RT: 0.01-1.28 AV: 99 NL: 2.64E9
T: FTMS - p ESI Full ms [150.0000-2000.0000]

obsd 681.2316, calcd 681.2310

¹H NMR spectrum of mero77 (DMSO-d₆, 500 MHz).

Peaks marked with * correspond to diisopropylethyl ammonium cation

